

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK S Gbearing USN6SU19OP001 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUTHA M KURUP bearing USN6SU19OP002 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms POORNIMA Mbearing USN6SU19OP003 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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